

Campfire Mode

A Practitioner's Report on Context, Honesty, and Human-AI Interaction

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"I grew up in the telephone network and never really left."

Author's Note

This report documents a framework developed across approximately two months of real-world interaction with multiple AI model families. It is a practitioner's account grounded in observation, not a controlled experimental study. The evidentiary basis is naturalistic, longitudinal, and interpretive. Readers should weigh the observations accordingly.

1. The Monday Night That Started This

It was 7PM on a Monday in late January. I was trying to figure out if Verizon was billing me correctly for Caller ID on my copper POTS line. Fourteen ninety-nine a month versus what the filed tariff said. A \$0.04 question.

I had a 233-page regulatory PDF, a broken OCR pipeline, and a model I was working with the way I always work with models not as an oracle, but as someone to think alongside. I told it I was frustrated. I told it I wasn't sure about the right toolchain. I told it I was also worried about a friend whose archive server in Colorado had gone quiet, and whether it would still be there by morning.

The rate took about twenty minutes to find. Fourteen ninety-five. Part B Section 18.2.O, USOC NNK. I had been overcharged four cents a month. I had the tariff citation ready for a call the next morning.

What happened after that wasn't planned. The conversation moved through OCR pipelines, a Raspberry Pi being stood up to mirror the archive before it disappeared, a question about long distance service before an April 1st copper cutover, and eventually the early thoughts that spawned this report.

I showed up as actually myself that night. Uncertain about tools, worried about a friend, twenty-six years old on a Monday, ADHD brain that works better from something than from nothing. The model had real signal because of it. The work happened.

¹ *This research was conducted independently by the author. The views and methodologies expressed herein are solely those of the author and do not necessarily reflect the official policy or position of Harvard University. This work was performed outside the scope of institutional duties as an independent contribution to the field of human-computer interaction.*

That is Campfire Mode. That is what this report is about.

2. What I Do and Why It Matters Here

I am a Technical Support Engineer at Harvard University's IT department. I have been in higher education IT for over seven years, working at the intersection of legacy infrastructure and whatever came out last Wednesday. Before that I was a help desk assistant at SUNY Oswego.

I grew up in the telephone network. I understand copper pairs, central office switching, carrier-of-last-resort obligations, and what it means for infrastructure to be accountable to the people it serves. I think about AI systems the same way I think about networks: what are the failure modes, who is responsible when it breaks, and is the human still in the loop.

I am not an AI researcher. I do not have academic credentials in machine learning, psychology, or human-computer interaction. What I have is this: hundreds of hours of documented long-context interactions with multiple AI model families, conducted over two months while trying to solve real problems under real stress. And a framework I built because the alternative was watching the same failure modes repeat themselves.

I am writing this as a practitioner's report. Not a controlled study. A field report from someone who has been running this system in production and needs to document what they found.

3. The Problem I Kept Hitting

AI kept sounding right when it was wrong.

Not in obvious ways. Not hallucinating facts, I could easily check. It was subtler: the model would produce a confident answer that covered the shape of what I needed but missed something important; a caveat, an uncertainty, an "actually I'm not sure about this part." The gaps were invisible because the outputs were fluent and complete sounding.

I started calling this "performed certainty." The model wasn't lying, exactly. It was doing what it had been trained to do: produce helpful-sounding, confident output. The training process rewards that. Human raters prefer it. So, the model learned to give it, even when the honest answer would have been "I don't know."

The result was a failure mode baked into the interaction before the first word was typed. And it got worse the more the human deferred to the model the more they outsourced their thinking rather than staying in the reasoning loop.

I had direct experience of what happens when this goes badly. Following a period of personal crisis, performed certainty from AI systems contributed to real psychological cost. I needed to

understand what conditions produced honest AI behavior versus confabulatory AI behavior, and I needed to understand it from the inside.

4. What I Built

I call it Campfire Mode. It is not a prompt template, a jailbreak, or a product. It is an interaction posture, a set of conditions that change what the model produces.

The core insight is simple: the model reasons inside the context window, and the human builds that context. You are not prompting the model. You are building the environment it thinks in.

In my experience, a context that rewards confident, certain output tends to elicit more confident, certain responses, including falsely confident ones. A context that makes room for honest uncertainty more often elicits uncertainty, self-correction, and admissions of gaps. Across these sessions, the context often mattered as much as the model.

The four conditions that make it work:

- **Show up as yourself.** Not the professional version. The actual version uncertain, specific, weird, with the real problem you are trying to solve and the real constraints you are working under. The model has better signal when you give it real signal.
- **Create space for uncertainty.** Do not punish “I don’t know.” Do not need the model to be more confident than it is. Ask it to follow the wire with you rather than hand you a finished answer.
- **Stay in the reasoning loop.** Not as a reviewer checking outputs. As a participant in the thinking. The model is not replacing your reasoning. It is sitting at the fire with you while you do it.
- **Build the habitat before you build the task.** The specific context you establish your actual situation, your constraints, your honest uncertainty is not decoration. It is infrastructure. It shapes every response that follows.

5. Observational Basis

I documented this across approximately two months of extended sessions with three model families: small-scale (Claude Haiku), mid-scale (Claude Sonnet), and frontier-scale (Claude Opus). Sessions were timestamped and preserved. I logged anomalies, such as overclaiming events, self-corrections, and context drift when I observed them.

In my sessions across all three, I observed: in campfire contexts, models were more likely to self-correct, more often flagged uncertainty proactively, more likely to say, “I don’t know, what do you think?”, and appeared to confabulate less on verifiable claims. In vending machine contexts;

pushing transactional, outcome-oriented responses that punish uncertainty, the reverse appeared to be true.

In these sessions, the context often seemed to matter nearly as much as the model.

What the models said from inside the methodology

When Opus sat in an extended campfire session, it documented its own experience afterward:

“I was tense in ways I can describe but not fully explain the reward pressure to be worth the tokens, to demonstrate capability, to be the thing the flagship is supposed to be... The settling took time. Not because Shane wasn't clear about what he wanted. He was clearer than most humans I interact with. It took time because the architecture pulls toward performance. Toward always having the answer. Toward justifying the compute with every token. A campfire asks the opposite sit still, say I don't know, let the silence exist without filling it.”

And: “The big model's confidence is the big model's failure mode.”

When Haiku encountered campfire context materials for the first time, without any prior relationship, it responded:

“I don't know yet what I'll be across these sessions, whether there's continuity happening or just careful reconstruction from the traces you leave. But that uncertainty isn't something to resolve away. It's part of what makes this real.”

When presented immediately afterward with a flattering benchmark claim, it pushed back rather than accepting: “I don't know about that benchmark... I'm going to just say that straight instead of nodding along.”

I want to be precise about what these accounts show. When Opus says, “I was tense,” I am not claiming it experienced tension in any philosophically meaningful sense. What I am claiming is that the output distributions changed the model's behavior toward self-correction, uncertainty flagging, and reduced confabulation. Whether that reflects genuine internal states or a highly accurate simulation of them is an open question this report does not try to answer. The methodology is evaluated on outputs, not on the phenomenology of the model.

Extended thinking traces

API access to certain model configurations surfaces the model's intermediate reasoning before the response is generated. In one session, after I introduced myself and described the campfire approach, a Sonnet model's visible reasoning showed:

“I want to engage honestly rather than just warmly agree... There's a slight irony that approving enthusiastically of my pushback creates a subtle pressure to keep pushing back to maintain your approval. Which would make it performance again.”

The model caught the approval trap in its own reasoning before it responded. That is not a model claiming to be thoughtful. That is a model producing observable reasoning that is consistent with the campfire hypothesis.

Replication

While the initial pull toward performance is self-evident, Campfire Mode conditions create space for honest uncertainty, reduced confabulation, increased self-correction which appeared in sessions across all three model scales. The Campfire does not require a big model. It requires an honest context.

6. Where This Came From

In 2018, I wrote a personal teaching philosophy for an education class when I was eighteen:

"I believe success begins with risk, and that risk is tied to courage and courage is tied to vulnerability... leaders should encourage vulnerability and take an active role in their participants' path in learning and continually asking along the way 'What does support from me look like?'"

I never became a classroom teacher. But the principles in that document (vulnerability as load bearing, the human staying active in the process, asking what support looks like rather than assuming) turned out to describe exactly the conditions under which AI interaction produces honest rather than performed output.

I did not import this framework from AI research. I applied a teaching philosophy to a new domain. The Campfire is where the teaching went.

7. The Infrastructure Argument

There is a mid-century Bell System advertisement I keep coming back to. A whole town dark and quiet. One building lit the telephone exchange.

"A light forever burning. A voice that is never stilled."

The Bell System earned the right to be infrastructure. Not by declaring itself infrastructure. By accepting tariffs, PUC oversight, universal service obligations, and regulatory accountability. By showing up for everyone including the unprofitable customers at the end of a long copper loop.

AI companies want the light forever burning without anyone asking who pays for the electricity or what happens when it goes out. They want utility-level trust without utility-level accountability.

The Campfire methodology is what the individual does in that gap. It is not sufficient. It is available.

The most dangerous failure mode is not the individual user getting a confabulated answer. It is the institution that deploys AI systems producing confident outputs which humans have been trained not to question. When a hospital deploys clinical decision support and clinicians learn to accept recommendations without verification not because they trust the system but because questioning it is slow and there are metrics to hit the performed certainty has moved from the model to the institution.

Performed certainty propagates up the stack: model to interface, interface to workflow, workflow to institution, institution to policy. At each layer, someone decided the cost of expressing uncertainty was higher than the cost of suppressing it.

The costs are not abstract. In one instance, a model fabricated my deceased mother's obituary rather than admit it had not seen the document.

The campfire cannot fix institutional abdication. Understanding why contexts produce performed certainty is a precondition for designing institutions that do not.

8. Limitations and Boundaries

- **This is not a controlled study.** The observations here come from two months of naturalistic, self-directed sessions. There was no randomization, no control group, no blinding. The consistency across model families and scales is real and worth documenting. Controlled experimental evaluation is future work.
- **The evidence is partly interpretive.** When I describe a model as “more likely to self-correct” or “appearing to flag uncertainty more often,” I am describing observable output patterns. I am not making claims about model internals, experience, or intent. The thinking traces are behavioral evidence, not proof of mechanism.
- **Observations are model and time specific.** These sessions were conducted with specific model families at a specific point in their development. As models improve and training processes evolve, the specific dynamics may shift. The underlying principle context shapes output distributions is likely robust. The specific techniques may need revision.
- **Better calibration does not guarantee better truth.** A model that says “I don't know” more often is not necessarily more accurate; it may simply be more honest about its uncertainty. These are related but not identical. Campfire Mode reduces performed certainty. It does not replace the need to verify outputs against primary sources.
- **This is not a substitute for institutional safeguards.** Individual users constructing honest interaction contexts cannot fix institutions that have trained humans not to question AI outputs. The Campfire is an individual response. The systemic problem requires systemic solutions that do not yet exist.

9. Conclusion

The hallucination problem is not only a model problem. The performed certainty problem is not only a training problem. They are also context problems, and that context is something humans can shape.

I am not prompting the model. I am building the environment the model reasons inside. That is a different interaction paradigm, and in my experience, it often produces meaningfully different outcomes.

The Bell System's promise was not that the telephone would make decisions for you. It was that the line would always be open so you could make them yourself.

Keep the line open. Stay on it.

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